

TYPES OF ADVERTISING TEXTS AND THE PRIORITY OF THEIR INFLUENCE ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY THROUGH COLORS

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Abstract. This article is about the types of advertising texts and the priority of their influence on human psychology through colors, how colors are used in marketing, and the definitions given to them, as well as in attracting the attention of consumers and It is widely covered what marketers need to focus on when purchasing.

Key words and phrases: advertising text, marketing, marketer, consumer, buyer, design, technology.

As we live in today's era of advanced science and technology, we cannot imagine our life without mass media and social networks. Therefore, when we look at the surrounding environment, we involuntarily look at advertising texts and posters. What are good ad texts, and when were the first ads created? and what types are there? What feelings do the colors in advertising texts evoke in customers? We can find answers to these questions below.

According to the definition of the French scientist Armand Deyan: "Advertising is a paid, one-way and impersonal appeal carried out through mass media and other forms of communication in favor of any product, brand, company." . The main purpose of advertising is to stimulate demand for the offered goods. Advertising tasks: stimulating demand and forming the needs of the population; development and expansion of the market for the sale of goods; speeding up the turnover of goods, achieving a balance between supply and demand; formation of consumer culture and development of aesthetic taste. Based on the above information, if we define the advertising text, it is aimed at customers to buy or use a certain product or service, usually to remain in the memory of readers, viewers and consumers in general, and to increase the consumption of the population. It is a type of text that serves to promote goods, has synthesis, accuracy, originality and harmony, and is made up of a title, picture, slogan and short text.

Although the term advertising first entered our speech in the 1850s, the use of advertisements goes back a long time. An example of this is an advertisement for the sale of a slave written on a papyrus in Egypt, preserved in the British Museum. This letter contains the following information: He (that is, the slave) has two ears that hear well, both eyes that see well, I guarantee that he is satisfied with food, obedient, and honest. From the text of this advertisement, we can see that there was a high demand for slaves during this period. Also, it was a requirement of that time to take into account the health of the slaves and the safety of the person buying the slaves.

Advertising texts are divided into the following according to their general description and methods of use:

- o exhibition advertisements;

- o advertising in the press;
- o print advertisements;
- o poster-graphic advertisements;
- o movie advertisements;
- o radio advertisements;
- o lighting ads.

It is the most common type of exhibition advertising and advertising. The main task of exhibition advertising is to introduce to consumers the assortment of goods that are available in the trade and intended for sale, to widely promote goods that are not yet familiar or unknown to consumers, to demand is to remind consumers of the need to buy goods suitable for a certain season that is approaching.

Depending on the content, advertisements are divided into targeted and emotional types. Targeted advertising describes the specific benefits that the consumer will receive from purchasing this product, while emotional advertising is designed to influence people's feelings and arouse positive thoughts about the product. It can be concluded from the above definitions that the main purpose of the advertising text is to have a wide audience for the advertised product. However, it should not be forgotten that when advertising a product, it is appropriate to proceed from the customs, outlook and mentality of the society where the product is being advertised. Here we pay attention to the words of the American economist Theodore Levitt: Advertising must obey its audience in universal life. Otherwise, it will be a scam. - he said. Based on the above comments, it is worth mentioning that it is not enough to advertise or sell a product, it is necessary to pay attention to its aesthetic aspects. Advertising can be watched not only in separate places, but also in the family circle.

Since Islam is life, he satisfies all his wishes and desires based on his psychology. He reacts to the events that occur in his life according to his psychology. Therefore, the surrounding colors are not an exception. When preparing an advertisement, the advertised product will stand out from other advertisements and attract the consumer's attention only if it has a unique name and color. The effectiveness of the psychological effect of advertising on the consumer is characterized by the number of coverage of consumers, the brightness and depth of the impression that these media leave on the human memory, and the level of attention. So, let's talk about what color evokes emotions in people in advertising.

In the field of marketing, each color has its own definition.

- • Yellow and optimism, certainty and warmth;
- • Yellow and optimism, certainty and warmth;
- • Red-excitement, youth, attention;
- • Black - Creativity, wisdom, understanding;
- • Blue - trust and power;
- • Green-freedom, growth and health;
- Gray means neutrality and peace.

The image below shows advertising stamps associated with colors.

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Advertising activities often use visual, auditory, taste, motor, smell, and some other types of senses. Here, the problem of studying the emotions caused by the perception of advertising or the consumption of an advertising product becomes relevant. This goal is achieved by measuring the emotions a person experiences when consuming the advertised product. If the resulting feelings are significantly different from those already known, the advertiser can distinguish the product and therefore influence the consumer's purchasing behavior. Psychological studies have shown that the sensations that a person experiences from objects that affect him are subject to Fechner's psychophysiological law. This law shows that at very large values of the stimulus, a person experiences smaller changes in sensations than at large values. Law also says that very strong effects (loud sounds, bright colors, detailed text) are not always the best for perception. Sometimes it is more effective to reach out to a person using less intensive means. (R.I. Mokshantsev, 2000) Another important element of human cognitive activity is perception. Unlike sensations, perception is a holistic reflection of things and events in the cerebral cortex. This reflection is accompanied or mediated by the conceptual apparatus, that is, it is indicated by the word, the name of the thing that a person perceives. By type, perception is similar to the senses: sight, hearing, smell, taste. Perception is often done meaningfully. Recognition plays an important role in the process of perception. In the perception of advertising information, the formation of a perception image, which has the most significant influence (or does not influence) on the buyer's behavior, plays a very important role. Special studies have shown that people are inexplicably loyal to, for example, a

brand of cigarettes or beer or other products that have a wide range of products. But with special tests, they cannot distinguish one brand from another. Three hundred smokers who preferred one of the three main types of cigarettes were offered the same three types of cigarettes, only without the names. They should know their favorite varieties. Out of three hundred subjects, only six were able to recognize the brand of their cigarettes. Psychologists came to a simple conclusion - people, in particular, "smoke the image, the image of cigarettes", not the brands of cigarettes. The main task of advertising is to create images of goods in the minds of consumers in a competitive environment that will encourage them to buy the advertised item. This is more true because many goods are standardized. Therefore, each brand needs to choose a design and color for a product that is not like others.

Summing up from the above information, it can be said that the advertisement should not only be beautiful, quiet, but also have a unique color and character. Only then will the product have its own brand and a wide sales area.

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